

Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation (IDEAS-QA4EO)

Final Report

WP-2191: Validation of TROPOMI Aerosol Height products with EARLINET observations

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Executive summary

The purpose of our study is to investigate the ability of the TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) on board on the Sentinel-5P, to deliver accurate geometrical features of lofted aerosol layers in a continental scale. Comparisons with ground-based correlative measurements constitute a key component in the validation of passive satellite products related to aerosol properties. For this purpose we have developed and applied an optimal methodology, using ground-based lidar data from lidar stations belong to EARLINET network. We are looking for collocated cases between EARLINET and TROPOMI/SS5P overpasses for the time period 2018 – 2024, across the Europe which is selected as the domain of interest. This report contains validation results using the latest version of the ALH algorithm (v02.06.00) implemented since November 2023. The new version introduces the surface albedo in the Optimal Estimation feature vector, producing more elevated ALH for both land and ocean. The quantitative validation analysis [May 2018 – August 2024], based on the latest version 02.06.00 (Level 2, RPRO+OFFL), over the EARLINET stations illustrates that TROPOMI ALH over ocean is consistent with calculated lidar ALH, with a correlation coefficient $R=0.66$ and mean bias of 1.46 km. In addition, over land, an agreement of $R = 0.56$ and a mean bias -0.49 km is found. These associated differences can be attributed to the different sensitivities of the TROPOMI and Lidar ALH measurements, as well as the applied spatiotemporal collocation criteria. Moreover, as part of the investigation into the performance of version 02.06.00, a comparative analysis with previous versions was performed, against EARLINET stations for a selected number of cases. The quantitative analysis illustrates that TROPOMI ALH over ocean is consistent with ALH_{bsc} , with a correlation coefficient $R=0.68$ and mean bias 1.41 km for the latest version (Prev. version: $R: 0.74$ /MB: -0.62km). Over land, an improved agreement of $R=0.51$ and mean bias -0.47 km is found (Prev. version: $R: 0.43$ /MB: -2.2km). It is clearly seen that with the implementation of the new version (v02.06) the number of processed pixels has increased significantly, both on land and at sea. It is also important to note that for the pixels retrieved, the distribution shows a significant increase in height levels. The mean layer heights are on average higher for TROPOMI over ocean and lower over land compared against the lidar measurements.

1 Introduction

In the following, we present the final report on the activities performed within the European Space Agency Quality Assurance for Earth Observation, QA4EO, project, Work Package 2191, entitled: “**Validation of ESA EO Aerosol Height products with EARLINET Lidar observations**”. The tasks of WP-2191 involve: **(i)** Validation of the aerosol layer height product (ALH) from TROPOMI/S5P using archived lidar measurements by EARLINET stations on operational basis, **(ii)** development of an automated algorithm for the validation needs, **(iii)** determination/optimization of the satellite and ground-based retrievals settings, **(iv)** Assessment of the performance of different TROPOMI/S5P ALH processing

versions, **(v)** Investigating the influence of critical factors on the use of vertical lidar profiles based on specific sensitivity tests.

For the purposes of this work, European Aerosol Research Lidar Network ([EARLINET](#)) data records for the period 2018 to 2024 were acquired and post-processed with the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics, LAP/Auth, dedicated software in order to identify lofted aerosol layers and exclude all cases of cloud presence contamination. The [S5P/TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height](#) dataset were download and post-processed so as to study the possible effects of other geophysical parameters of the satellite L2 algorithm in order to clearly identify aerosol layers. The dedicated LAP/Auth Aerosol Validation Chain was then applied to the entire timeline. The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height product has a number of important applications, notably for aviation safety purposes, but also for a range of scientific research themes. A large-scale global validation of the Aerosol Layer Height product is essential to understand the quality and performance of the sensor and algorithm. In recent years, many Earth satellite sensors have developed algorithms to extract the Aerosol Layer Height (ALH) information from their ultraviolet/visible (UV/VIS) observations: the MetOp Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment-2 (GOME-2) instruments (Hassinen et al., 2016), the Deep Space Climate Observatory (DSCOVR) mission with its Earth Polychromatic Imaging Camera (EPIC) (Xu et al., 2019), the Multi-angle Imaging Spectro-Radiometer (MISR) on board the NASA Terra satellite (Nelson et al., 2013), the Sentinel-5P TROPospheric Monitoring Instrument (Veefkind et al., 2012), and more recently the Geostationary Environment Monitoring Spectrometer (GEMS; Kim et al., 2019). Upcoming missions such as the Sentinel-4 and Sentinel-5 missions (Ingmann et al., 2012) are expected to continue providing quality-assured aerosol height data sets. Since the altitude of aerosols is difficult to determine from space using passive sensors, validation processes are best carried out with active satellite aerosol remote sensing observations or ground-based lidars. Due to the variable distribution of aerosols in space and time, an accurate validation against independent ground-based measurements is needed in order to evaluate the quality of the TROPOMI retrievals. This report is structured as follows: **Section 1** contains the description of the different satellite and ground-based data sets. **Section 2** contains the detailed description of the validation strategy, the quality control and product limitations. In **Section 3** we provide the main validation results and statistics as well as specific sensitivity tests, so as to demonstrate the full potential of presented method. Finally, conclusions and prospects are summarized in **Sect. 5**

2 Data and Methodology

A short description of instruments and data used in this study is presented in next sub-sections, including a short explanation on the methodology that we followed for validation purposes.

2.1 European Aerosol Research Lidar Network | EARLINET

Lidar is the most prominent tool for aerosol profiling and has largely contributed to our knowledge of the vertical distribution of the aerosol optical properties (e.g., Balis et al., 2004, Amiridis et al. 2009; Mona et al., 2012). The European Aerosol Research Lidar Network (Pappalardo et al. 2014) established in 2000, provides an excellent opportunity to offer a large collection of quality-assured ground-based data of the vertical distribution of the aerosol optical properties over Europe. The geographic and temporal coverage of EARLINET stations as well as the reported quality assured measurements provides an excellent framework for the intercomparison of TROPOMI/S5P products under different atmospheric conditions and aerosol concentrations. Ground-based lidar measurements provide backscatter profiles and in some cases extinction profiles. These profiles can unambiguously indicate the presence of aerosol and cloud layers. If the optical thickness of the aerosols and clouds takes high values, then multiple aerosol and cloud layers can be detected. Information on aerosol properties and aerosol type is sometimes also available, depending on the specific lidar technique (Klett et al. 1981, Fernald, 1984, Ansmann et al., 1992). The majority of the EARLINET stations are equipped with multi-wavelength Raman channels and many of them operate depolarization channels that measure the depolarization of the emitted linearly polarized radiation. In order to ensure qualitative and consistent data processing within the EARLINET network, algorithm intercomparison campaigns have been organized (e.g. Amodeo et al., 2020). Since the lidar networks are designed with long-term observation in mind, the EARLINET is also a suitable source for the long-term validation for the TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height data product. Data from lidar measurement EARLINET network can be used on a case study basis to evaluate specific aerosol episodes or they may be compiled into a larger validation set comprising many validation sites over a longer period of time to allow for a statistical analysis. EARLINET data have been used extensively for satellite aerosol product validation in recent years, such as for the Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations (CALIPSO) (Winker et al., 2009), which is the first satellite focused on monitoring vertically resolved aerosol and cloud optical products (Papagiannopoulos et al., 2016). Furthermore, the evaluation of aerosol optical products from the Cloud-Aerosol Transport System (CATS) on board the International Space Station (ISS) was also performed based on the EARLINET database (Proestakis et al., 2019). Recently, the co-polar particle backscatter coefficient product measured by the Atmospheric Laser Doppler INstrument (ALADIN) on board Aeolus was evaluated in the Iberian Peninsula using EARLINET data (Abril-Gago et al., 2022). With respect to the aerosol layer height reported by UV-VIS satellite sensors, Michailidis et al. (2021) have successfully validated the GOME2/MetOp absorbing aerosol height (AAH) products using aerosol profiles reported by the EARLINET community. The intercomparison showed that the GOME-2 AAH measurements provide a good estimation of the aerosol layer altitudes sensed by the EARLINET ground-based lidars with a mean bias of approximately 1 km. While the TROPOMI ALH has more observations of dust and smoke outflows over the water surfaces, the GOME-2 AAH has improved availability over desert regions and remote oceans as its retrieval has no constraint on surface albedo and cloud fraction.

Figure 1 illustrates the geographical locations of the selected EARLINET stations involved in the TROPOMI–EARLINET intercomparison (listed alphabetically: Antikythera-PANGEA, Athens, Barcelona, Bucharest, Clermont-Ferrand, Dushanbe, Évora, Granada, Lecce, Leipzig, Limassol, Minsk, Potenza, Sofia and Thessaloniki). All participating stations operate high-performance multi-wavelength

lidar systems. Table 1 provides details of these stations, including their identification codes, coordinates and surface elevations, which were used for the validation of the TROPOMI/S5P ALH product.

EARLINET stations contributing to TROPOMI/S5P ALH validation

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of EARLINET lidar stations (see Table 1) for which co-locations with S5P L2 AER_LH data were used (period May 2018 – August 2024).

Most of EARLINET stations involved are based on multi-wavelength Raman lidar systems, which combine detection channels at both elastic and Raman-shifted signals and are equipped with depolarization channels. Observations submitted to the EARLINET database follow absolute accuracy standards to achieve the desired confidence in product calculations. To this end, the lidar measurements are processed by the single calculus chain (SCC) (D'Amico et al., 2015, 2016), the standardized tool that allows a centralized process of the lidar data acquired at each station within EARLINET. All the operations implemented in SCC modules are designed to preserve both the vertical and time resolution as high as possible. Some instrumental effects (like for example, dead-time correction, trigger-delay correction, overlap correction, atmospheric and electronic background subtraction, low- and high- range automatic signal glueing) are corrected following the recommendations provided by the EARLINET quality assurance program.

The main information provided by the EARLINET database is the vertical distribution of aerosol backscatter and aerosol extinction coefficients alongside their errors at one or more out of the following wavelengths: 355, 532, and 1064 nm. The database also includes volume and particle depolarization ratio profiles at 532 nm (some stations also at 355 nm). During the daytime, the data acquisition is limited to the signals that occur from the elastic scattering of the laser beam by the air molecules

and the atmospheric aerosol. The Klett–Fernald (KF) inversion is applied (Klett, 1981; Fernald, 1984), and the backscatter coefficient profiles are produced. In this study, only daytime lidar data from the QA EARLINET database were considered. A common source of uncertainty when dealing with lidar data is the system's overlap function that determines the altitude above which a profile contains trustworthy values. The incomplete overlap between the laser beam and the receiver field of view significantly affects lidar observations of particle optical properties in the near-field range (the first few hundred metres).

Table 1. Locations of EARLINET lidar stations order by site, with their geographical coordinates and TROPOMI cases considered in the validation process.

Station	Code	Country	Longitude, latitude, elevation
Antikythera	AKY	Greece	23.31°E, 35.86°N, 193m
Athens	ATZ	Greece	23.78°E, 37.96°N, 212m
Barcelona	BRC	Spain	2.12°E, 41.3930°N, 115 m
Bucharest	INO	Romania	26.03°E, 44.34°N, 93 m
Clermont-Ferrand	PUY	France	3.11°E, 45.7610°N, 420 m
Dushanbe	DUS	Tajikistan	68.85° E, 38.55°N, 864 m
Évora	EVO	Portugal	7.91°W, 38.56°N, 293m
Granada	GRA	Spain	3.60° W, 37.16°N, 680m
Lecce	SAL	Italy	18.10°E, 40.33°N, 30m
Leipzig	LEI	Germany	12.43°E, 51.35°N, 125 m
Limassol ^{1,2}	LIM	Cyprus	33.04°E, 34.67°N, 10m
Minsk	MAS	Belarus	27.60°E, 53.91°N, 200 m
Potenza	POT	Italy	15.72°E, 40.60°N, 760m
Sofia	SOF	Bulgaria	23.38°E, 42.65°N, 550 m
Thessaloniki	THE	Greece	22.95°E, 40.60°N, 50 m

¹Cyprus University of Technology (CUT) [before Oct 2020]

²Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research and ERATOSTHENES Centre of Excellence [after Oct 2020]

2.2 Lidar layer height retrievals

A common product of all lidar observations is the profiling capability, that is, the aerosol layering. In order to characterize the detected aerosol layers, in terms of their geometrical properties, parameters such as the layer base (Z_{BASE}), layer top (Z_{TOP}), layer thickness (L_{TH}) and center of mass (Z_{COM}), can be calculated from the lidar signals. In this study, we make use of the weighted-backscatter height

(ALH_{bsc}), calculated as the center of mass on backscatter profile, based on the methodology described in Mona et al. (2006). This height parameter is an important indicator for vertical profiles that gives in a single number an indication of the altitude of the aerosol distribution. In cases where a single aerosol layer is present in the atmosphere, the ALH_{bsc} gives an indication of its mean altitude; in case of multiple layers however, the ALH_{bsc} could be located in areas without any considerable aerosol load. This parameter is considered ideal for comparisons with aerosol layer height retrievals from passive remote sensing (e.g. TROPOMI/S5P and upcoming Sentinel-4 & 5 missions).

Furthermore, in our study we apply the WCT approach following the work proposed within Michailidis et al. (2021) for automatic layer detection (see Appendix A for details on a case study). Once the top and base of the aerosol layer are identified, the center of mass of each aerosol layer can be also estimated from lidar profiles. Information about the aerosol layer center of mass is useful because the characteristics of the detected layer can be distinguished at this altitude. Under the detection of a homogenous aerosol layer, the center of mass can be estimated as the mean altitude of the identified aerosol layer weighted by the altitude-dependent aerosol backscatter coefficient. In some cases, the aerosol vertical structure is very complicated because aerosol layers are present at different heights. For these cases a total layer resulting from the multilayered structure is considered for the calculation of mean optical parameters and integrated values. The weighted-backscatter altitude is estimated by the equation:

$$ALH_{bsc} = \frac{\int_{z_i=1}^{z=n} z_i \cdot \beta_{aer,i}(z) dz}{\int_{z_i=1}^{z=n} \beta_{aer,i}(z) dz} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where $\beta_{aer,i}$ represents the aerosol backscatter coefficient ($Mm^{-1} \cdot sr^{-1}$) primarily at 1064 nm channel at level i and Z_i is the altitude (km) of level i for the aerosol profile signal. Based on the above equation, the layer height is calculated from backscatter profiles, symbolized as ALH_{bsc} . The ALH_{bsc} represents an effective ALH weighted by the aerosol backscatter signal at each level and is consistent with ALH as defined in the TROPOMI algorithm. In our work analysis, we applied **Eq. 1**, to all lidar backscatter profiles collocated to TROPOMI measurements.

2.3 TROPospheric Monitoring Instrument | TROPOMI

The TROPospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI; Veefkind et al., 2012) instrument is a space-borne, nadir-viewing, imaging spectrometer covering wavelength bands between the ultraviolet and the shortwave infrared. Sentinel-5P is a near-polar sun-synchronous orbit satellite flying at an altitude of 817 km, with a 2600 km wide swath, providing near-daily global coverage and overpass local time at ascending node of 13:30 (repeat cycle of 17 days). TROPOMI uses passive remote sensing techniques to attain its objective by measuring, at the Top Of Atmosphere (TOA), the solar radiation

reflected by and radiated from the earth. The spatial resolution at nadir, originally of $3.5 \times 7 \text{ km}^2$ (across-track \times along-track) has been refined to $3.5 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$ on 6 August 2019.

- **TROPOMI/S5P Aerosol Layer Height (AER_LH)**

The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height (AER_LH) product is a new operational TROPOMI product with little heritage focusing on the retrieval of vertically localized aerosol layers in the free troposphere, such as desert dust, biomass burning aerosol, or volcanic ash plumes. It can therefore provide accurate values to the modelling community by improving air quality forecasting and radiative forcing studies. The height of such layers is retrieved for cloud-free conditions and is reported in both altitude and pressure. The aerosol height retrieval is based on the absorption in the Oxygen A band in the near-infrared wavelength range (759–770 nm) and assumes a single aerosol layer of 50 hPa thickness. This is an important simplification to note when comparing with other satellites and ground-based lidar profiles (e.g. from EARLINET), since these lidar profiles have the capability to detect multiple aerosol layers. The Oxygen A band can provide altitude information on scattering layers (clouds or aerosol) from the troposphere up to the stratosphere. The TROPOMI aerosol layer height (AER_LH) algorithm was developed by the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI; Sanders et al., 2015; Nanda et al., 2018, 2020) and is a part of the TROPOMI operational algorithm suite. In the context of this study, the offline and reprocessed (OFFL + RPRO) daily TROPOMI data were used, under the versions 02.04, 02.05 and 02.06 for the period 2018-2024, accessible through the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>, last accessed: 15 April 2024). In brief, for this product, several quality control filters are applied in the TROPOMI L2 dataset, following the filtering proposed for ALH product (Nanda et al. 2020; Table 1). Detailed description of the changes can be found in appropriate versions of the Product User Manual (PUM; Apituley, et al., 2024) and Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD; de Graaf, et al., 2023) associated with the ALH product. The corresponding data are filtered with a quality assurance value greater than 0.5 ($qa_value \geq 0.5$), ensuring mostly cloud-free observations, according to PUM (Apituley et al. 2024, last access: 01 October 2024). A comprehensive description of the TROPOMI ALH product as well details about the algorithm's principle is available in Nanda et al. (2018), whereas the validation performance status in Michailidis et al. (2023).

Additionally, we also employ the operational TROPOMI UV aerosol index (UVAI) product (Stein-Zweers et al., 2021) to assess the extent of the detected aerosol plumes across the area of interest. The UVAI serves as an air quality metric obtained from the top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) reflectance spectra and is commonly utilized as an indicator of absorbing or scattering aerosol species present throughout the atmospheric column. It relies on spectral contrast within the UV spectral range for a specific pair of wavelengths, where the disparity between the observed reflectance and the modeled clear-sky reflectance yields a residual value. This is ideal for tracking the evolution of extreme aerosol layers. Positive residual values indicate the existence of absorbing aerosols like smoke, dust or volcanic ash. Near-zero values usually signify cloud cover and negative residuals may suggest the presence of non-absorbing aerosols or optically thin clouds and aerosols over both land and oceans, as demonstrated in sensitivity analyses of the UVAI (e.g., de Graaf et al., 2005). As a result, although the UVAI yields as an initial indicator of aerosol presence, care is required as to its quantitative

interpretation. For the purposes of this work, only near cloud-free observations were selected with quality assurance values of 0.75 for AI ($qa_value \geq 0.75$), as recommended by the respective Product User Manuals (PUM; Apituley et al. 2023a, last access: 01 October 2024).

The TROPOMI pixel selection scheme and flags applied is enumerated here, following the recommendation by the Product User Manual (PUM) and Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD):

- i. Pixels with an associated quality assurance value of less than 0.5 were excluded.
- ii. Pixels with an associated negative UVAI are excluded, hence only desert dust, biomass burning aerosol and volcanic ash aerosols – i.e. absorbing aerosols – remain in the dataset.
- iii. Pixels with a raised sunglint flag are excluded.
- iv. Pixels over land are excluded, due to known surface albedo issues (Sanders et al. 2015).
- v. Pixels with an associated cloud percentage are excluded. Clouds strongly bias the TROPOMI ALH towards the cloud altitude. Additional cloud screening, which is available in the product in the form of flags, is essential for retrieving proper aerosol layer heights.

All the above quality control procedures and filtering criteria applied in the final dataset, are summarized in Nanda et al. (2020; **Table 1**).

2.1 Validation approach and spatiotemporal co-location criteria

EARLINET contributes a robust and extensive database encompassing continental-scale aerosol distribution information. For the routine validation of the S5P/TROPOMI aerosol layer height retrievals, the automated validation server in LAP-AUTH deployed within the IDEAS-QA4EO project (WP 2191; Michailidis et al. 2023) collects S5P ALH data and correlative measurements to identify suitable co-locations, compares to the co-located data, and produces S5P data quality indicators. A purpose-built automated tool, called ATLANTIS, was developed at AUTH to facilitate these validation tasks. The approach followed is mostly based on the previous expertise and methodology that have been developed and applied in EARLINET for the GOME2 cal/val activities (Michailidis et al., 2021). Taking into account the recommendations of the previous comparison studies (e.g. Griffin et al., 2020; Nanda et al., 2020), the selection of data and the comparison between TROPOMI and the EARLINET datasets estimates of aerosol heights proceed through the following steps, for each date:

1. Make a list of TROPOMI overpass swaths that are within the region of interest (EARLINET stations).
2. Identify the closest TROPOMI pixels (within a radii of 150km) around EARLINET stations in time and space. A maximum time difference of $\pm 3h$ is allowed between collocation pairs.
3. For each ground-based measurement, the spatially averaged TROPOMI pixels in a radii of 150km, were selected for the comparison study.

4. As input to the validation processing, we use the lidar backscatter coefficient profiles at 1064 nm (or 532 nm), analyzed by the Single Calculus Chain (SCC) algorithm (D'Amico et al., 2015, 2016) for quality-assured measurements and TROPOMI Level-2 OFFL and RPRO ALH product.
5. In order to make an accurate validation analysis we apply quality screening flags, to eliminate samples and layers that were detected or classified with very low confidence or that contained untrustworthy height retrievals. Furthermore, EARLINET observations have been carefully checked, and atmospheric conditions have been studied to ensure that cloud-scenes are excluded from the profiles.
6. For the layer height retrieval from the EARLINET products, we used the methodology proposed by Mona et al. (2006) to calculate the weighted backscatter height using the Level-2 backscatter profiles 1064 nm (or 532nm). Furthermore, we apply the WCT method in order to identify the aerosol layer boundaries from the detected layers.

It should also be noted that the temporal criterion is necessary since most of the EARLINET lidar observations occur at noon or night. To reduce mismatch errors due to the significant difference in horizontal sensitivity between S5P and lidar measurements, individual TROPOMI ALH data, are averaged over a selected radius around the study stations.

3 Validation Results

3.1 Consolidated validation analysis

A comprehensive statistical analysis regarding the distribution of the absolute differences between the TROPOMI against EARLINET ground-based lidar observations for spatiotemporal collocated ALH products are presented in detail through this section. Data from fifteen stations were considered in this analysis and were compared to S5P L2_AER_LH (RPRO +OFFL) v02.06.00 data for the period from May 2018 until August 2024. Regarding the use of the reprocessed TROPOMI AER_LH data product, the Product Algorithm Laboratory (PAL) was implemented. The geographical distribution of the selected EARLINET stations depicted in Figure 2 indicates the domain of applicability of the validation results. All participating stations operate high-performance multi-wavelength lidar systems. The location of the stations across the European continent is an ideal test environment for TROPOMI ALH features due to their proximity to the Sahara Desert and Europe, with frequently observed events of mineral dust and smoke particles. The TROPOMI aerosol layer height product can be examined under a complete set of different atmospheric conditions. A significant number of selected cases (dust and smoke scenes) have been analyzed demonstrating the promising performance of the proposed algorithm under various aerosol loading scenarios over different surface surfaces (ocean/land). Overall, the statistical results demonstrate the potential of the TROPOMI instrument to detect aerosol layers under cloud-free atmospheric conditions with significant aerosol load, such as dust and smoke plumes. The ALH product was tested over both land and sea. Over land, the TROPOMI ALH product has

decreased detection capabilities than over the sea surfaces since, over bright surfaces, the retrieval algorithm becomes increasingly sensitive to errors in the surface albedo features.

The results of the comparison between the TROPOMI L2_AER_LH (RPRO+OFFL; v. 02.06.00) and EARLINET-derived aerosol heights for all the identified collocated cases between May 2018 and August 2024, are shown in **Figure 2** in the scatterplot of TROPOMI ALH against EARLINET ALH_{bsc} for all common cases (over land: N = 117, over ocean: N = 97) used for the intercomparison. By defining a weighted height from EARLINET aerosol backscatter profile products (ALH_{bsc}), the quantitative validation at pixels over the selected EARLINET stations illustrates that TROPOMI ALH over ocean is consistent with ALH_{bsc}, with a high correlation coefficient $R=0.66$ and mean bias 1.46 km. Over land, less good agreement is found ($R = 0.56$ and mean bias -0.49 km). The yellow solid line is the linear fit line between the datasets. The colour scale indicates the averaged TROPOMI aerosol index values. Overall, the TROPOMI ALH retrievals are systematically lower than the corresponding lidar heights in both clusters. This can also be seen in **Figure 2** (bottom), which presents histogram plots of their absolute differences, which appear lower for land pixels (left Figure in green) and increase for the for ocean pixels (right Figure in blue).

Figure 2. (Top panel) TROPOMI ALH (v02.06.00) against EARLINET data for pixels over land (left) and ocean (right) for the period from May 2018 to August 2024. Colour-scale indicates TROPOMI retrieved UVAI (388/354nm) values, vertical error bars indicate the standard deviation of the spatial average of the TROPOMI ALH pixels. (Bottom Panels) Histogram of absolute difference between TROPOMI and EARLINET ALHs, shown in green for land pixels (left) and red blue the ocean pixels (right).

The S5P data used overall in the study are produced under the ALH algorithm versions 02.06.00. Within this study the authors use the maximum number of available EARLINET cases, to avoid any possible selection effect resulting from a poor sample of correlative cases, when strict collocation filters are applied.

- **Dust case over the Central Mediterranean: 30 June 2024, Potenza (Italy)**

A typical dust intrusion day with sufficient aerosol load over the Central Mediterranean was selected to illustrate the performance of the TROPOMI ALH product over a scene with sufficient aerosol load. On 30 June, the central Mediterranean was affected by a strong dust episode originating from North Africa. On this day, the TROPOMI overpass over Italy was between ~12:00 and 13:00 UTC. A lofted layer of dust was also clearly observed by the MUSA lidar system at Potenza station on the same day. MUSA is the lidar system deployed at CNR-IMAA Atmospheric Observatory (CIAO) in Potenza (40.60°N, 15.72°E, 760 m a.s.l.). The dust plume can clearly be seen in **Figure 3** over Italy from the VIIRS/Suomi-NPP true-colour image for this day. In **Figure 4** TROPOMI S5P UV (at 340/380nm) aerosol index (left) and ALH values (right) are plotted over the Italy showing the spatial extent of the dust plume generated by Saharan desert on 30 of June. Elevated dust layers appear to be detectable, especially for high aerosol index values. Comparing the TROPOMI product maps to the VIIRS image, it can be seen that the large positive UVAI pixels and elevated aerosol layers are located at the detected plumes. It is noted that data gaps in the ALH map represent screened-out bright pixels due to either cloud, bright land surface or due to algorithm failures.

Figure 3. VIIRS/Suomi NPP true-colour image for the dust scene on 30 June 2024 over Italy (generated from NASA Worldview Snapshots: <https://wvs.earthdata.nasa.gov/>).

Figure 4. (Left) UV Aerosol index (340/380nm) and (right) Aerosol Layer Height (ALH) from the TROPOMI instrument aboard Sentinel-5P across dust plume on 30 June 2024. TROPOMI ALH spatial distribution based on based on v02.06.00 algorithm processing version. The Potenza EARLINET station is depicted with a red dot.

Figure 5 illustrates the mean aerosol backscatter profiles at 1064 nm derived from MUSA lidar at Potenza for the time between 14:30-15:30 UTC. The backscatter profile that is closest in time is used in order to extract the ALH_{bsc} and compare it against TROPOMI ALH retrievals. The lidar analysis by applying the Wavelet Covariance Transform (WCT) technique reveals a clear single dense layer between 1.6 and 5.5 km with maximum backscatter value $\sim 2.8 \text{ Mm}^{-1} \cdot \text{sr}^{-1}$ and a center of layer mass at 3.2km (orange dashed-line in the left Figure). For the selected case, a notable discrepancy between lidar and TROPOMI layer identification was found. The mean layer heights are on average higher in altitude for TROPOMI over ocean and lower over land surface compared against lidar measurements, respectively. Applying v.02.06.00 the TROPOMI observations report an average layer at $2.1 \pm 0.9 \text{ km}$ over land (green line) and $4.2 \pm 1.1 \text{ km}$ over sea (blue line), respectively. The calculated ALH_{bsc} from the lidar profile places it at 2.9km (magenta line).

Figure 5. Averaged Backscatter lidar profile obtained at 1064nm from MUSA lidar system at Potenza station, close to Sentinel-5P overpass (14:30-15:30). The corresponding ALH values are marked with different colors (within a radius of 150 km from the lidar station).

3.2 Assessment of the latest S5P AER_LH algorithm version

In the framework of ESA IDEAS-QA4EO, a detailed comparison analysis was performed to test the latest S5P AER_LH processor version (v02.06) against previous versions (v02.04, 02.05), which was carried out for the 2018 – 2023 period, using the archived collocated TROPOMI-EARLINET datasets for a selected number of cases. The reprocessed TROPOMI AER_LH v02.06 data product provided by the Product Algorithm Laboratory (PAL) was used on this scope. The results of the comparison between the different TROPOMI L2 AER_LH algorithm versions against EARLINET-derived aerosol heights for collocated points between 2018-2023, are presented in Figure 6 and Figure 7 separately over ocean and land surface, respectively. The colour scale indicates the averaged TROPOMI aerosol index values. Regarding the latest 02.06 version, the quantitative validation at pixels over the selected EARLINET stations illustrates that TROPOMI ALH over ocean is consistent with ALH_{bsc} , with a correlation coefficient $R=0.68$ and mean bias 1.41 km (Prev. version: $R: 0.74$ /MB: -0.62km). Over land, an agreement of $R = 0.51$ and mean bias -0.47 km is found (Prev. version: $R: 0.43$ /MB: -2.2km). Specific flags have been applied [$QA \geq 0.5$, $UVAI > 0$] within a distance radius of 150km around the EARLINET stations. It is clearly seen that with the implementation of the new version (v02.06) the number of processed pixels has increased significantly, both on land and at sea. It is also important to note that for the pixels retrieved, the distribution shows a significant increase in height levels. The mean layer heights are on average higher for TROPOMI over ocean and lower over land compared against the lidar measurements.

(A) Investigation of the performance of S5P/AER_LH over Ocean

Figure 6. Scatterplots of TROPOMI against EARLINET data over land for $QA \geq 0.5$ and $AI > 0$ within a radius of 150km around ground-based stations. (left) S5P AER_LH v02.04 & v02.05, (right) S5P AER_LH v02.06. Color-scale indicates TROPOMI-retrieved UVAI values, error bars correspond to the spatial variability of the averaged TROPOMI ALH pixels. Data filters: $QA \geq 0.5$, $AI > 0$, within 150km from ground-based stations.

(B) Investigation of the performance of S5P/AER_LH over Land

Figure 7. Same as Figure 6, including only Land surface pixels.

The statistical metrics are also shown in the inbox text and also are given in **Table 2** for ocean and land satellite retrievals. It is clearly seen that with the implementation of the new version (v02.06) the number of processed pixels has increased significantly, both on land and at sea. It is also important to note that the distribution shows a significant increase in height levels. The mean layer heights are on average higher for TROPOMI over ocean and lower over land surface compared against lidar. The obvious overestimation of the aerosol layer height retrieved by the current algorithm from TROPOMI over ocean is probably related to the cloud-affected scenes, leading to biased or non-convergent retrievals. Thresholds for cloud-filtering are not rather strict where optically thin clouds can bias the retrieval of aerosols. Additionally, according to the findings, the previously observed large bias over land has been reduced since the surface albedo fitting was included in the retrieval procedure in the latest processor version.

Table 2. Statistics of the comparison between TROPOMI ALH and EARLINET ALH data sets, under different algorithm processor versions, over ocean and land surface respectively.

AER_LH Version	Number of points	Mean Bias [km]	Pearson (R)
Over Ocean			
v02.04 / 02.05	74	-0.62±0.92	0.74
v02.06	74	1.41±1.77	0.68
Over Land			
v02.04 / 02.05	65	-2.2±1.23	0.43
v02.06	65	-0.47±1.59	0.51

Overall, the quantitative statistical results presented above indicate that the updated algorithm version has enhanced the data quality of S5P ALH. However, further investigation is needed to validate these findings, including an analysis of how cloud presence impacts retrievals and whether the new version accurately identifies the upper boundary of the highest detected layer when compared to lidar signals. Specific sensitivity tests should be conducted to examine biases and standard deviations in the retrieved aerosol height, particularly in cases of cloud contamination, such as optically thin and thick cirrus clouds, and low-altitude broken cumulus clouds, using different flagging masks.

- **Case study: Massive summer fires in Northern Greece during August 2023**

At the end of August 2023, a series of wildfires took place in northern Greece resulting in thousands of square kilometres of Evros region being burned and causing a huge amount of smoke to enter the troposphere. The emissions caused extreme air pollution conditions with poor visibility throughout the area for several days. This wildfire stands as the largest blaze ever recorded in the EU by the European Forest Fire Information Service (EFFIS) since the beginning of its data collection, in 2000 with around 90.000 hectares burnt. Most of the burnt area is concentrated in the Dadia Forest. The TROPOMI sensor has been monitoring these wildfires and tracked the smoke as it travelled to arrive in Thessaloniki LAP-AUTH station. During 22 August, the fire intensity grew rapidly under the influence of strong north-easterly winds. Fire fronts expanded rapidly outwards, creating a large burnt area. The plume is visible in Figure 8, acquired in the afternoon on August 23, 2023, by the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) on the NOAA-NASA Suomi NPP satellite. The fires resulted in widespread smoke aerosol clouds and extremely large UVAI values.

True colour image VIIRS/Suomi-NPP [23 August 2023]

Figure 8. True-colour image captured by VIIRS on board Suomi-NPP satellite platform (<https://worldview.earthdata.nasa.gov/>) on 23 August 2023.

Figure 9 (left) depicts the daily spatiotemporal evolution of the smoke plume from the Evros wildfires event, indicated by the regions with extremely increased UV aerosol index (UVAI) levels observed on 23rd of August 2023, as captured by TROPOMI. The high positive values reveal the strong presence of absorbing aerosol load, clearly illustrating that the smoke emissions from the occurred fires were transported westerly all the way to Thessaloniki and the surrounding domains. The right panel of Figure 9 display the corresponding daily maps of TROPOMI ALH retrievals for the same days, illustrating the spatial coverage of the retrieved ALH pixels. In the case of the dense smoke plume, ALH retrieval effectively captures the plume with better spatial coverage, encompassing the elevated smoke altitudes along the coastline.

Figure 9. Spatial distribution of TROPOMI aerosol index (UVAI; left panel) and Aerosol Layer Height (ALH; right panel) retrievals during the smoke plume transport over Greece, for the 23rd and of August 2023. The LAP site is located at the center of the black circle.

From the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics (40.6° N, 22.95°E; 60 m a.s.l.), which is located on the Department of Physics in Thessaloniki (~270 km away from Alexandroupoli), systematic measurements have been collected and used. A sun/sky photometer of the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) is continuously operated in LAP. This allows the study of optical and microphysical properties of detected aerosol plumes. The smoke led to unusually high aerosol optical depth (AOD) values (up to 3.6 at 340 nm) as can be seen in Figure 10 (left). The presented case study indicates that the spatial variations of smoke plume height have significant implications in the aerosol atmospheric column. To further investigate the source and transport of the wildfire plumes, the Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model (Stein et al., 2015) was employed (Figure 10, right). HYSPLIT is used over the regional to global scale to account for the transport of pollutants, their dispersion, and deposition. In this analysis, 7-day backward trajectories ending at 12:00 UTC for Thessaloniki (LAP-AUTH), were generated using Global Data Assimilation System meteorological data at seven levels varying from 1 to 6 km, with an interval of 1 km above ground level. A combined analysis of such data information is critical for classifying and clustering aerosols into different categories.

Figure 10. (Left) Daily variation in spectral aerosol optical depth during the wildfire event at Thessaloniki AERONET station. (Right) 7-days air mass back-trajectories arriving at different altitudes above Thessaloniki (indicated by a yellow star) on 23 August [12:00 UTC]. The trajectories are superimposed on VIIRS/Suomi-NPP true-color images. MODIS fires and thermal anomalies are shown as red dots.

That day was selected to illustrate the performance of the new algorithm processing version (v02.06.00) of TROPOMI ALH product. The performance of the TROPOMI ALH is recorded under different spatial distances around the lidar station and over different surface type (sea/land). The equivalent daily spatial distribution of S5P ALH retrievals are shown in Figure 11 for applied for version 02.05.00 and 02.06.00, respectively, over a wide area centered at the Thessaloniki site. The three colored circles indicate a radius of 50, 100, and 150 km around the site. The contrast observed between land and sea regarding the retrieval of the ALH product and the surface albedo values is obvious, as can be seen from the color scale in ALH retrievals.

Figure 11. TROPOMI ALH spatial distribution based on (left) V02.05.00 and (right) V02.06.00 algorithm processing versions. The Thessaloniki EARLINET station is depicted with a red star.

Table 3 shows the results of the statistical analysis for different spatial radius limits around the LAP station, as well as for a different type of surface compared to the previous version. Over land the average value of TROPOMI marks the value near 6 km, higher than the average value along the entire profile, and 4 over land. In comparison it seems to overestimate the recovery value of the lidar. In order to have as representative a comparison between TROPOMI-Lidar observations as possible, a radius distance of 50 km around the Thessaloniki station was used. Recall that so far in earlier validation reports, a radius of 150km has been used due to the reduced number of converged pixels over land.

Table 3. Statistical metrics for the TROPOMI ALH averaged over circles with increasing radius around the Thessaloniki site. Mean TROPOMI ALH averaged over circles centered at the Thessaloniki site with increasing radius, as a function of that radius (expressed in km).

S5P Over Ocean					
Radius ≤ 50km		Radius ≤ 100km		Radius ≤ 150km	
V.02.06.00	V.02.05.00	V.02.06.00	V.02.05.00	V.02.06.00	V.02.05.00

6.04±1.46 (31)	1.52±0.42 (31)	1.61±0.47 (183)	6.04±1.46 (185)	4.81±1.35 (514)	1.58±0.62 (533)
S5P Over Land					
3.09±1.62 (307)	0.81±0.47 (100)	3.08±1.73 (671)	0.85±0.49 (229)	3.03±1.73 (986)	0.9±0.47 (339)

* The number of retrieved pixels is noted in parentheses.

Figure 12 shows the frequency histograms of the previous and latest processing algorithm versions (v02.05 in blue, v02.06 in red), separately over sea and land, respectively. It is clearly seen that with the implementation of the new version the number of pixels recovered has increased significantly, both on land and at sea. It is also important to note that for the case of pixels retrieved with the new version over sea the distribution shows a significant increase in height levels. We apply our validation process using satellite retrievals separately over land and water surfaces to further demonstrate the known TROPOMI ALH issues over land.

Figure 12. Frequency histograms of TROPOMI ALH retrievals under the version v02.05.00 (red) and v02.06.00 (red). A separate analysis for detected pixels over sea (left) and land (right) has been performed.

Figure 13 (left) illustrates the temporal evolution of the observed aerosol plume by means of the time–height cross sections of the 1064 nm total attenuated backscatter coefficient for the time period from 11:00 to 13:00 UTC on the 23 August. The averaged backscatter lidar profile obtained at 1064nm is illustrated on the right panel. Blue color indicates weak backscattering, yellow–red colors in the range-corrected lidar signal indicate strong backscattering signal mainly from fine aerosols. The dashed red box indicates the temporal averaging of these lidar signals close to the S5P overpass time. On the right, the mean aerosol backscatter profiles at 1064 nm derived from THELISYS for the time period from 11:14 to 11:50 UTC is shown. The analysis reveals a clear single layer between 4 and 6km with maximum backscatter value $\sim 6.8 \text{ Mm}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$ and centre of layer mass at 4.9km. For the selected case, a notable discrepancy between lidar and TROPOMI layer identification was found, the reasons for which warrant further investigation in the future. Lidar measurements observed two stratified plumes, one around 0.5–2.3 km and one at 4–6 km. Applying v02.06.00 the TROPOMI observations report an average layer at $3.09 \pm 1.62 \text{ km}$ over land and $6.04 \pm 1.46 \text{ km}$ over sea, while for the version 02.05.00 the layer is marked at $0.81 \pm 0.47 \text{ km}$ and $1.52 \pm 0.42 \text{ km}$ respectively. The calculated ALH_{bsc} from the lidar profile places it at 4.2 km. In addition, the center of mass of each of the two detected layers is illustrated with orange color. TROPOMI ALH reported the smoke at much lower altitude than lidar observations.

Figure 13. (left) Temporal evolution of the Range-corrected at 1064 nm backscatter signals (in arbitrary units, A.U.) reflecting the atmospheric conditions over Thessaloniki, obtained by THELISYS lidar system for 23 August 2023. (Right) Backscatter lidar profile obtained at 1064nm. The average values are marked with a different color (within a radius of 50 km from the lidar station).

3.3 Evaluation of the TROPOMI-to-EARLINET ALH comparisons

Several factors can significantly influence the comparison between TROPOMI and ground-based lidar observations, which cannot be solely attributed to S5P data limitations or simple area-averaging discrepancies. In the framework of ESA IDEAS-QA4EO project, we demonstrate the ability of good quality lidar measurements, obtained from a selected number of EARLINET stations, to be used for the

validation of TROPOMI ALH satellite retrievals. The effect of various aspects such the terrain topography and the presence of single/multi-layers in the scene was systematically investigated through several sensitivity tests. Moreover, the effect of the overlap height and lidar ratio (LR) on the ALH lidar estimates, using lidar backscatter profile retrievals, has been investigated, based on specific assumptions. Specific sensitivity experiments have been also performed to test the effect of using observed aerosol vertical profiles.

- **Investigation the effect of the overlap height and Lidar Ratio selection**

The overlap assumption plays a crucial role in calculating lidar-based ALH for validating TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height (ALH). When using lidar data to validate satellite-based aerosol layer heights, understanding how the vertical profiles of the two instruments correspond to each other is essential. The incomplete overlap area between the laser beam and the receiver field of view can affect the observations of the optical properties of the particles in the first few hundred meters. If the overlap assumption is not properly accounted for, especially in the lower atmosphere, it can lead to an underestimation of aerosol height. Incomplete overlap near the surface reduces the lidar's sensitivity to aerosol particles at lower altitudes, making it seem as if the aerosols are located higher than they are. To overcome this issue, we rely on certain assumptions. In order to quantify the uncertainty of the ALH_{bsc} estimates due to assumption we made for tackling the incomplete overlap issue we performed a number of sensitivity tests. An example case over Thessaloniki on 15 June 2022 is presented in Figure 14 which demonstrates the effect of the overlap altitude on the lidar ALH calculation for different scenarios. Dashed colored lines correspond to the different indicative assumptions for the backscatter coefficient profile below the overlap height. The horizontal-colored lines indicate the corresponding lidar weighted height. The scenario with a negative slope of backscatter in lower part is indicated in green, the case for vertical extension (zero signal slope) in red, and the third with a positive slope in blue. After applying the above sensitivity tests to all lidar measurements used in the study, we can conclude that the effect of the different assumptions shown on the calculation of ALH_{bsc} is of the order of 100 - 400m, depending on the technical characteristics of each lidar system. It should be also noted that in the calculations described above, the altitude of the EARLINET stations is considered for the calculation of the ALH_{bsc} . Most stations are located at low altitude in coastal areas, so it does not play a significant role, in contrast to stations located at an altitude > 600m such as Granada and Potenza, where the effect is significant.

Figure 14. Sensitivity test to define the effect of overlap altitude on ALH_{bsc} calculation under different scenarios (Thessaloniki 15 Oct 2022)- Dashed lines correspond to the different overlap assumption.

Furthermore, we also studied the effect on the ALH_{bsc} estimates based on lidar backscatter profile retrievals for different Lidar Ratio (LR) values (20–60sr). We assumed: (a) constant values of the lidar ratio with height and (b) LR height dependent profile. The results show that in both cases the effect of the different lidar ratio values on the weighted height calculation (ALH_{bsc}) is small, lower than 40m.

- **Investigation the effect of Topography**

The topography can affect the satellite-ground based intercomparison of measurements/products. Over areas with a complex terrain, vertical inconsistencies between ground-based and satellite retrievals, due to possible orography induced disturbances in the aerosol layer height. It should be also noted that the use of a circular sampling area around the sites may not always be the optimal choice for the comparison since the Aerosol layer height variability is not necessarily symmetric due to the effects of local topography on the aerosol transport. In order to study the effect of topography on the TROPOMI ALH retrievals the authors separated the EARLINET stations used in the study, into 2 separate clusters: Coastal (Limassol, Lecce, Antikythera, Athens) and Mountainous (Potenza, Granada, Evora). According to the findings, it is evident that the correlative measurements between the Mountainous EARLINET stations and the S5P overpasses are characterized by higher variability, more extreme differences, higher mean biases than in the Coastal cases. The complex topography, in terms of geographical characteristics, the horizontal distance between the TROPOMI retrieved pixels and the ground-based lidar sites possibly enhance the discrepancies resulting in higher differences between the EARLINET and TROPOMI values. The quantitative analysis illustrates that TROPOMI ALH over ocean is consistent with ALH_{bsc} , with a correlation coefficient $R=0.68$ and mean bias 1.41 km for coastal

stations and $R=0.83$ and mean bias of -0.61 for Mountainous regions. Over land, the agreement for coastal areas is $R = 0.51$ and mean bias -0.47 km, where for Mountainous is found $R=0.68$ with mean bias of -2.67 . However, we should note that these findings are based only on limited satellite retrievals and we will need more data to better justify this conclusion.

- **Investigation the effect of the detected layers**

The structure of atmospheric aerosol layers is a challenging task for a passive sensor affecting ALH. A separate analysis for the cases where only one layer was detected and for the cases where two-or-more layers were detected by EARLINET, has been investigated through this work. Following the work proposed by Michailidis et al. (2021) for automatic layer detection, we also apply the wavelet covariance transform (WCT) approach in order to check whether the TROPOMI-retrieved ALH is sensitive to distinct layers rather than a representative effective layer from the whole profile. In this methodology all possible individual layers identified by the lidar observations are analyzed autonomously, providing individual assessments on the height of the aerosol mass and not a mean effective height from all layers as is extracted by Eq. (1). In the case that more than one layer with a significant contribution to the optical thickness of the profile exists, an average value between these is calculated for the comparison against satellite height retrievals. Several cases where distinctly separated elevated and boundary layer aerosols are present in the same scene – satellite product derives one layer. Overall, lidar data reveal the presence of a single aerosol layer in 58.3% of sample cases and a multilayer structure (two-or-more layers) the 41.7% of the total sample cases. Regarding the results, the mean bias of the difference between S5P and EARLINET seems to become larger when multilayers exist in the atmospheric scene, but we cannot say with certainty that it is the general rule due to the use of a limited validation dataset. Overall, among all the cases the best performance of TROPOMI is recorded in case of single well-developed dust layers.

4 Summary and Conclusions

The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height (ALH) product offers a unique capability for global observations of aerosol height, with potential to significantly benefit the modeling community by enhancing air quality forecasting and supporting improved studies on air quality and radiative forcing. A key advantage of TROPOMI's aerosol plume height retrievals is its ability to provide daily global coverage. The report presents a cross-comparison analysis of TROPOMI and EARLINET datasets, proposing a well-structured methodology to facilitate this comparison. As lidar instruments retrieve vertical backscatter coefficients, which are not directly comparable to the TROPOMI ALH product, appropriate techniques must be employed for meaningful comparison. This final report contains validation results using the upgraded version of the ALH algorithm (v02.06.00) implemented since November 2023. The new version introduces the surface albedo in the Optimal Estimation feature vector, producing more elevated ALH

for both land and ocean. The consolidated and quantitative validation analysis between the period from May 2018 to August 2024, based on the latest version 02.06.00 (Level 2, RPRO+OFFL), over the EARLINET stations illustrates that TROPOMI ALH over ocean is consistent with calculated lidar ALH, with a correlation coefficient $R=0.66$ and mean bias of 1.46 km. In addition, over land, an agreement of $R = 0.56$ and a mean bias -0.49 km is found. These differences can be attributed to the different sensitivities of the TROPOMI and Lidar ALH measurements, as well as the applied spatiotemporal collocation criteria.

Within the frame of IDEAS-QA4EO, this study highlights the importance of the synergistic use of active and passive observations and suggests a promising usage of TROPOMI ALH observations for understanding the details of the presence and transport of aerosol layers. The results of this study encourage the operational usage of the presented methodology approach in validation processes for satellite aerosol height products using lidar data from EARLINET. The increased availability of advanced and high quality-assured profiling data from EARLINET lidars will form a scientific background to improve performance of passive satellite sensors and lead to better understanding the role of the aerosol height on air-quality and the climate. For this reason, the further development of the validation methods is an on-going process in the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics (LAP-AUTH) aiming at extending the study domain from the regional to continental scale, considering the TROPOMI/S5P algorithm improvements provided by KNMI for ALH retrievals.

Appendix A: Automated Aerosol layering - Wavelet covariance transforms (WCT)

In the frame of IDEAS-QA4EO, an automated algorithm was developed for the operational validation of S5P Aerosol Height product using lidar observations performed by EARLINET stations. This section aims at illustrating how the Wavelet covariance Transform (WCT) method can be used on Lidar backscatter profiles for layer detection. We use the wavelet covariance transform following the scheme proposed by Michailidis et al. (2021). The aerosol geometrical properties carry information about the structure of lidar profiles, such as the boundary layer height and the features of the lofted aerosol layers, and can be obtained from any lidar profile. In this study, a full lidar dataset from 7 EARLINET stations has been used for the calculations. Some lidar optical products, however, are more reliable to use than others. For example, the longer wavelengths typically magnify the differences in the vertical distribution of the aerosol load, resulting in layers that are easier to identify. Furthermore, the Raman inversion always results in profiles that are less structured for the extinction coefficients than the backscatter coefficients. This is the reason why we prioritize them so as to produce geometrical properties. The product with the highest potential to magnify the aerosol layer structure available is selected for each measurement. A critical parameter for the accurate WCT application is the selection of an appropriate value for the window (dilation), so as to distinguish cloud layers from aerosol

layers. In our case, a dilation of 0.5 km is used for the selected backscatter profiles according to Baars et al. (2008). Then, the algorithm scans the profile, searching for pairs of boundaries (base-top). The PBL value is the first top layer (the first aerosol layer), with the ground being its basis. Details about the WCT method can be found in Siomos et al. (2018) and Michailidis et al. (2021).

An example of a lidar backscatter profile with resulting WCT profile from the Thessaloniki (LAP-AUTH) lidar station 29 August 2019 is given in Figure A 1. This figure shows the ability of the lidar to detect multiple layers. The horizontal dashed blue and red lines represent the detected aerosol layer base and top applying the WCT methodology, and two aerosol layers are detected, according to the followed methodology.

Figure A 1. Thessaloniki Lidar System (THELISYS): (Left) lidar backscatter profile at 1064 nm and (Right) resulting WCT profile on 29 August 2019 (Details as figure) The horizontal dashed red and blue lines represent the detected aerosol layer top and base applying the WCT methodology. The label “S–G” indicates that a Savitzky–Golay filter was used to signal smoothing. The yellow horizontal line represents the center of mass for each detected layer.

Data availability

The TROPOMI/S5P observations are currently publicly available from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>, last accessed: 01 October 2024). EARLINET data used in this study are available from the authors and upon registration from the EARLINET web page at: <https://data.earlinet.org/earlinet/login.zul> (Pappalardo et al., 2014). Satellite True color images are available at the NASA Worldview application (<https://worldview.earthdata.nasa.gov>, last access: 01 October 2024). Sun-sky photometer data are accessible on the AERONET website (<http://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/>, last access: 01 Oct 2024). The Lidar Quicklooks are available via the EARLINET web page (<https://quicklooks.earlinet.org/>, last access: 01 October 2024).

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